

InteGRated systems for Effective ENvironmEntal Remediation

greener

NEWSLETTER

Issue 6, April 2023

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The GREENER project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 826312

1. WORLD WATER DAY 2023

This year on March 22nd the World Water Day was celebrated focusing on “accelerating change” to solve the water and sanitation crisis. This fits to the United Nations’ Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 6: Clean water and Sanitation. In 2015, when the SDGs were set the vision was that everyone would have safely managed water and sanitation by 2030. Currently, billions of people and countless schools, businesses, healthcare centres, farms and factories seem to not have access to water and sanitation .

The UN 2023 Water Conference, 22-24 March, was the place where solving the water and sanitation crisis was discussed. This Conference will launch the **Water Action Agenda** , which will include commitments from people around the world.

GREENER Project includes SDG 6 along with others (SDG 9, 13,14 and 15) in its priority actions.

www.worldwaterday.org/learn

GREENER is close to its end and has aimed to identify and characterise different mixture of contaminants in surface and ground waters. Several bioremediation technologies for polluted surface and ground water have been developed and validated at lab scale, both individually and integrated in hybrid systems for enhanced treatment. In particular the project has succeeded to achieve i. dyes removal by novel approaches in phycoremediation, ii. optimization of phytoremediation technology for toxic metals and metalloids removal, iii. development of bio-electrochemical systems for TPHs, pesticides, antibiotics and PAHs removal, iv. development of a novel technology for metal removal as nanoparticles from biological systems, and v. development of an integrated system for effective groundwater bioremediation. Followingly, after defining the operation conditions for the scale-up for water remediation technologies pilot scale projects were validated and tested in selected locations of interest. Moreover, reduction of energy demand during bioremediation technologies to the minimum necessary related to processes and transport was achieved followed by bioelectricity generation through microbial fuel cells.

2. MICROTECHWEEK 2022 AND GREENER MEETING

GREENER Project teamed up with **SURFBIO project** to organise the WEEK OF MICROBIAL TECHNOLOGIES, that took place during 7-11 November in Józef Stefan Institute, in Ljubljana and online! The event was co-organised by JSI, UBU and AXIA.

The event gathered experts in the field of surface and colloid biology, biotechnology, environmental protection, and bioremediation technologies, as well as stakeholders and researchers in applications related to food, health, materials, and environmental solutions. You may visit the dedicated website designed by our coordinator University of Burgos: <https://www.microtechweek.com/home>

During this event the 42M meeting of the GREENER Project took place along with open public events, such as an industrial workshop including a poster session and a hands-on training, to transfer knowledge regarding the applications of surface and colloid biology in different industrial sectors.

2. MICROTECHWEEK 2022 AND GREENER MEETING

The industrial workshop was a great opportunity for industry members to learn about the latest developments in these fields, and to discuss the challenges and potential solutions with other experts. The topics covered included:

- surface and colloid biology
- biotechnology
- environmental protection and
- bioremediation technologies

Attendees had the chance to socialize and exchange opinions with experts in materials science, as well as from specialists in health, food and environmental applications. Moreover, some of our relevant projects shared their views, including BIOSYSMO, BIOVALUE, and DIAGONAL, among others. The workshop was followed by a poster session, along with a 3 minutes flash presentation, offering the opportunity to interact among a significant number of researchers involved in different EU projects.

Followingly, a hands-on training focused on the “Experimental and computational approaches to study cell-cell interactions and cell-surface interactions” was organised. The training offered several lectures by well-known researchers followed by a demonstration session and a laboratory practical.

Finally, a 1.5 day of GREENER meeting led to very productive discussions on the achievements and the work to be implemented until the project's end, on August 2023.

3. GREENER TALK

Check out our new talk with Mendel University in Brno, where Dalibor Huska gave an interesting presentation focusing on the use microalgae in the remediation Process of Azo Dyes. "Microalgae have emerged as a promising tool for the remediation of azo dyes due to their ability to remove and degrade these pollutants from contaminated water" he states.

**CHECK IT OUT
ON YOUTUBE!**

A screenshot of a video player showing a presentation slide titled 'Microalgae in remediation' from Mendel University in Brno. The slide also lists 'Dr. Ioanna Katsavou, Project Manager, EXELISIS' and 'Dr. Dalibor Huska, Researcher at Mendel University in Brno'. The video player interface includes a 'greener' logo, a 'GREENER Talk' banner, and two video thumbnails. The date '14 February 2023' is displayed below the video player. At the bottom of the slide, logos for Mendel University in Brno, AXIA INNOVATION, and exelisis are shown, along with the European Union flag.

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**GREENER Talk with
Mendel University of Brno**

14 February 2023

Mendel University in Brno
AXIA INNOVATION
exelisis

Microalgae in remediation

Dr. Ioanna Katsavou, Project Manager, EXELISIS
Dr. Dalibor Huska, Researcher at Mendel University in Brno

14 February 2023

4. OUR NEW PUBLICATIONS

	Partner	Title	Journal/Book
PUBLICATIONS IN JOURNALS			
	University of Bath	Functionalised graphite felt anodes for enhanced power generation in membrane-less soil microbial fuel cells	RSC Sustainability
	University of Burgos	Sustainability of phytoremediation: Post-harvest stratagems and economic opportunities for the produced metals contaminated biomass	Journal of Environmental Management
	University of Burgos	Comparative toxicological assessment of three soils polluted with different levels of hydrocarbons and heavy metals using in vitro and in vivo approaches	Environmental Pollution
	NTU	Biosynthesized iron sulfide nanoparticles by mixed consortia for enhanced extracellular electron transfer in a microbial fuel cell	Bioresource Technology
	University of Surrey	Integration of microbial electrochemical systems and photocatalysis for sustainable treatment of organic recalcitrant wastewaters: Main mechanisms, recent advances, and present prospects	Science of The Total Environment
	NTU	Quorum sensing signals from sludge improving the self-assembly of electrode biofilms in microbial fuel cells for chloramphenicol degradation	Environmental Science: Water Research & Technology
CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS			
	University of Burgos, LEITAT and TAUW	Integrated systems for effective environmental remediation"	Book of abstracts of the EBC-VIII conference, Crete, Greece.

5. DISSEMINATION EVENTS

Our coordinator Universidad de Burgos along with South East Technological University and Universidad Autónoma de Madrid attended the 3rd Global Soil Biodiversity Conference, in Dublin.

UBU gave a presentation titled: "Use of omics to determine microbial diversity of hydrocarbon polluted sites", while SETU and UAM participated with poster presentations depicting the results achieved under the GREENER project.

Find out more: <https://lnkd.in/evU6qrpK>

FIND OUT MORE!

Our coordinator University of Burgos is celebrating one more year the "International Day of Women and Girls in Science", on 11th February, by organising a series of workshops for children.

5. DISSEMINATION EVENTS

Mendel University in Brno organised a workshop on the 16th of November 2022, focusing on “Modern biotechnology and its impact on human life”. The seminar transferred knowledge about biotechnology, nanotechnology, and genetically modified plants, as well as their benefits and disadvantages for humans.

Find out more: <https://lnkd.in/d2J7aYNr>

Find out more: <https://events.iniav.pt/bemiplant>

Our partners Università degli Studi di Cagliari, LEITAT and University of Bath attended the 4th edition of the E3 Mediterranean Symposium: Electrochemistry for Environment and Energy (E3MS) conference on 15-17 Sept 2022, in Orvieto (Italy), with a presentation titled: BIO-electrochemical systems for the removal of pollutants from soil and water: a model-based study.

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid participated in the BeMiPLANT meeting at Oeiras on the 17th of October 2022. During their talk titled: “Bacterial synthetic communities (SynComs) as inoculants for agriculture and environmental protection” they presented GREENER Project H2020 results, as an invited speaker.

Find out more: <https://e3medsym.gei2022.it>

5. DISSEMINATION EVENTS

University of Burgos participated in the EUtalenton initiative, September on 14-18 September 2022! 104 scientists around Europe were selected to team up and address challenges under 5 missions. UBU participated in MISSION 05: "Soil deal for Europe", aiming to the transition towards healthy soils by 2030.

Find out more:: <https://talenton.eu>

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ICCRAM
INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH CENTRE IN APPLIED AND INDUSTRIAL BIOTECHNOLOGY

University of Burgos attended the 22nd world congress of soil science (31 July - 5 August 2022), where the GREENER outcomes were presented by our colleague Prof Carlos Rad.

Find out more:: <https://22wcso.org/>

5. DISSEMINATION EVENTS

University of Burgos invited presenters from Jozef Stefan Institute, where they gave a training on "Lego Microbes", highlighting GREENER Project H2020 technologies among others.

GREENER Project attended the ISMET8 conference and joined the European Corner along with the projects VIVALDI, ELECTRA and TRINEFLEX. All projects are aiming at developing bioremediation and sustainability strategies with innovative bio-electrochemical technologies.

Find out more: <https://www.ismet8.org/en/home>

ICCRAM (University of Burgos) participated one more year in the European Researchers' Night activities, presenting several projects, including GREENER. This is a public event where students and scientists can familiarise with technological developments.

Università degli Studi di Cagliari, LEITAT and University of Bath participated at the Regional (European) Meeting of the International Society of Electrochemistry during 15-19 Aug 2022, that took place in Prague.

Find out more: <https://lcms.cz/events/199>

5. DISSEMINATION EVENTS

Università degli Studi di Cagliari participated at the Conferences on Green Chemistry and White Biotechnology (8th Edition), that was held in Liege, on 28-29 Sept 2022.

Find out more: <https://www.greenwin.be/fr/page/conferences-chimie-verte-biotechnologies-blanches>

Our coordinator, Dr Rocio Barros, head of ICCRAM research group, participated as a keynote speaker at the 2nd International Conference on Climate Change & Environment which was held from 11 to 13 January 2023, in Islamabad (Pakistan), giving a presentation on "Sustainability and innovation:

Integrated systems for effective environmental remediation".

Jesús Ibáñez from UBU gave a talk in the 'Iberoamerican Online Conference of Circular Economy', an event in Spanish focusing on the key issues for economic recovery and circular transition in Iberoamerica.

Find out more: <https://orangeuniversity.org/conferencia-iberoamericana-de-economia-circular>

6. ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Check out the video presented by our coordinator University of Burgos, presenting GREENER Project, launched on the occasion of the World Congress of Soil Science. Their work was summarised in a poster presentation titled: "Use of biochar and rhamnolipids as enhancers of TPHs' bioremediation processes". During the video Dr. Roccio Barros presented the project aim, Mrs Sandra Curiel Alegre the materials and methods, Dr. Blanca Velasco-Arroyo presented the results included in their work, while the conclusions were given by Prof Carlos Rad.

NEW VIDEO!

6. ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

PRESS RELEASE

Rocío Barros y Blanca Velasco, investigadoras principales del proyecto BIOSYSMO. ©AMT OTSNO

Soluciones basadas en la naturaleza como respuesta a la contaminación

Varios grupos de investigación de la Universidad de Burgos junto a ICCRAM participan en el proyecto internacional BIOSYSMO que busca desarrollar tecnologías innovadoras y sostenibles para descontaminar suelos y aguas. **Davinia Andrés**

Según algunos estudios, más del 60% de los ríos españoles se encuentran contaminados y la principal causa son los aborres, vertidos industriales y herbicidas. De hecho, el madrileño río Manzanares ostenta el dudoso honor de ser el río más contaminado del continente. Aunque revertir esta situación no es tarea fácil, ya hay iniciativas que buscan poder cambiarla con nuevas herramientas que tengan la sostenibilidad como principal valor. El proyecto BIOSYSMO es una de ellas y en él participan quince instituciones, centros de investigación y empresas de siete países europeos, entre los que se encuentra, como uno de los principales socios científico-técnicos, la Universidad de Burgos con ICCRAM, su Centro Internacional de Investigación en Materias Primas Críticas para Tecnologías Industriales Avanzadas, y con los grupos de investigación UBU-COMP; Grupo de Investigación en Compostaje y RBT; Grupo de Biotecnología y Biotecnología.

Como explican las investigadoras principales del proyecto Rocío Barros y Blanca Velasco, los trabajos que se van a desarrollar van encaminados a generar nuevas tecnologías de biorremediación de suelos y aguas, estudiando en profundidad los microorganismos que están presentes en estos elementos contaminados para poder así aprovechar su potencial transformador de la contaminación. Gracias a este conocimiento se podrán establecer diagnósticos basados en biorremediación y fitorremediación para eliminar contaminantes como metales, pesticidas o hidrocarburos, entre otros, como destaca Rocío Barros. BIOSYSMO viene a dar continuidad a los cuatro años de trabajo que lleva el Centro de Investigación burgalés en el proyecto GREENER coordinado por la investigadora Rocío Barros, consolidando los conocimientos adquiridos en el campo de la de biorremediación y fitorremediación. Como explica Blanca Velasco, el objetivo de estas tecnologías es poder aprovechar la capacidad que tienen los microbios que están presentes en el suelo contaminado para

recorren esa polución que, por otro parte, les sirve de nutrientes y así ayudar a limpiar ese suelo. En el caso de la fitorremediación lo que se utiliza es la capacidad que tienen algunas plantas, por ejemplo, aquellas que crecen en las riberas de los ríos, para absorber metales y otros compuestos que están en las aguas y, por tanto, contribuyen a la depuración y limpieza de aguas contaminadas. El papel de la UBU será, principalmente, el de caracterizar el tipo de contaminación de las muestras con las que se va a trabajar y el perfil toxicológico que tienen antes de su tratamiento con herramientas de biorremediación. Otro de los objetivos que se desarrollará en la universidad burgalesa será el de continuar innovando en esas tecnologías dirigidas a descontaminar suelos y reducir así la presencia de hidrocarburos y pesticidas en los mismos, así como también disminuir la contaminación de agua donde están presentes metales tóxicos. La idea es estudiar el potencial de algunas plantas mediante

tecnologías de fitorremediación y continuar innovando con tecnologías de bioestimulación y bioasimilación para suelos. Una vez terminada el trabajo de laboratorio la idea es poder poner en marcha demostradores en diferentes emplazamientos reales para comprobar la eficacia de esta tecnología. De hecho, el que haya varias empresas implicadas como socios de la iniciativa hace que esa materialización esté más cercana a un producto final que se pueda llegar a comercializar en el mercado. Precisamente en este sentido se ha hecho un especial avance en el proyecto GREENER, ya que dentro de este contexto se ha desarrollado un sistema denominado 'bioplar' que está enfocado a la descontaminación de suelos a partir de la biorremediación. En el caso de las plantas, como destaca Blanca Velasco, ICCRAM cuenta con instalaciones donde se estimulará el crecimiento de varias especies sobre sistemas sencillos de aguas contaminadas para conocer cómo reaccionan y si son capaces de depurar correctamente esa

el trabajo previo realizado durante los tres últimos años, ya hay, en algunos casos, un desarrollo piloto de estas tecnologías con resultados muy interesantes y esperanzadores. Uno de los handicaps que tiene esta tecnología es el tiempo que se debe emplear para que tenga efecto en los procesos reales, ya que, al tratarse de procesos biológicos, es difícil acelerar las reacciones necesarias para una eliminación completa de los contaminantes en un corto espacio de tiempo. Para poder salvar esta situación, uno de los objetivos de BIOSYSMO es, precisamente, entender cuáles son los microorganismos que hay en ese suelo y cómo poder potenciarlos y estimularlos para que esa remediación sea más rápida y efectiva. Como destacan las investigadoras principales de BIOSYSMO, en las últimas semanas los socios que participan en este nuevo proyecto han asentado las bases para poder dar un paso más respecto a lo trabajado en el proyecto anterior, fijando objetivos más ambiciosos y, sobre todo, distribuyendo tareas enfocadas a determinar las muestras que servirán como objeto de estudio. Uno de esos planteamientos es poder utilizar tecnologías híbridas, es decir, combinar la biorremediación y la fitorremediación con otras herramientas como, por ejemplo, los sistemas bioelectroquímicos. Este proyecto está enmarcado en el programa de Investigación e Innovación de la Unión Europea 'Horizonte Europa' para el periodo 2021-2027 y tiene una dotación total de 5,7 millones de euros, de los cuales 500.000 euros destinados a la Universidad de Burgos.

University of Burgos (ICCRAM) Presented their work on soil and water decontamination through the development of innovative and sustainable technologies in the magazine Innovation of El Correo de Burgos newspaper.

PRESS RELEASE

Our project coordinator on behalf of the International Research Center on Critical Raw Materials for Advanced Industrial Technologies (ICCRAM) presented in a press release the 13 active projects founded under H2020 and Horizon Europe, consolidating their research lines.

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 ESTUDIOS ADMISIÓN Y MATRÍCULA INVESTIGACIÓN INTERNACIONAL LA UNIVERSIDAD

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ICCRAM comienza 2023 con dos nuevos proyectos europeos

El centro de investigación de materiales de la UBU consolida su posición en el marco europeo de investigación

ICCRAM, el Centro de Investigación Internacional en Materias Primas Críticas para Tecnologías Industriales Avanzadas adscrito a la Universidad de Burgos, comienza 2023 con dos nuevos proyectos, **Tribiome** y **Convert2Green**, financiados con un millón de euros por **Horizonte Europa**, el programa marco de Investigación e Innovación de la Unión Europea para 2021-2027. Un año más, con 13 proyectos activos, el centro continúa garantizando su estabilidad y consolidando sus líneas de investigación.

Tribiome tiene el objetivo de transformar y hacer más resilientes los sistemas de producción de alimentos a partir del estudio de los microbiomas (comunidad de microorganismos -como hongos, bacterias y virus-) que se encuentran en el suelo, las plantas, los animales y los humanos. Los investigadores se enfrentarán a retos como la necesidad de minimizar el uso de agroquímicos (fertilizantes y plaguicidas), reducir el impacto ambiental y promover una cadena alimentaria sana y sostenible, al tiempo que se

alimenta a una población mundial en constante crecimiento bajo el paradigma del cambio climático.

Para este fin, el proyecto tiene una duración de cuatro años y una asignación de casi 5 millones de euros repartidos entre 13 socios europeos, de los cuales ICCRAM-Universidad de Burgos capta unos 270.000. Está liderado por **Rocío Barros**, responsable del grupo ICCRAM-EST (Medioambiente, Sostenibilidad y Toxicología) y **Carlos Rad** del grupo de **Compostaje** del área de Edafología y Química Agrícola de la UBU.

Por otro lado, **Convert2Green** tiene como objetivo establecer un "Open Innovation Test Beds (OITB)", lo que se traduce en un "ecosistema abierto de innovación": un espacio que actúe como un banco de pruebas que permita a las empresas (proveedores de materiales) integrar soluciones innovadoras y sostenibles a sus cadenas de valor. Este sistema es una nueva forma de llevar la innovación al mercado, mediante la cual, los miembros del OITB ofrecen sus servicios especializados a empresas interesadas y buscan sinergias para facilitar el desarrollo tecnológico y la innovación en el espacio europeo.

Este proyecto cuenta con un consorcio de 17 socios y una asignación de 12 millones de euros en un

DATOS DE LA NOTICIA

Fecha:
Lunes 20 de febrero de 2023

Categoría:
Investigación

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CHECK THIS OUT!

6. ADDITIONAL DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

INTERNAL WORKSHOP

On September 15th Materia Nova, LEITAT and University of Burgos organised an internal workshop on: Technoeconomic Assessment (TEA), LCA and LCC, Social LCA, Energy Analysis and Regulatory and Risk Analysis. The discussions were followed by technical partners TAUW, LEITAT, University of Burgos, ACCIONA and SETU presenting diagrams and pilots and providing inputs regarding the Remediation Technologies of the GREENER project.

VISIT

GREENER Project partners University of Burgos, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid and Jozef Stefan Institute met on 30 September 2022 in UBU premises. They addressed the next steps for soil decontamination at laboratory scale and the actual scaling-up based on the results obtained throughout the project.

7. PLANNED ACTIVITIES

CLUSTERING WORKSHOP AND GREENER CONFERENCE

On the 28th of June GREENER Project will co-organise an interesting workshop along with 6 more projects on bioremediation (**MIBIREM**, **BIOSYSMO**, **SYMBIOREM**, **ELECTRA**, **EiCLaR**, and **NYMPHE**). The workshop will be held in MuttENZ, one day before the BioRemid 2023 conference.

On the same day, the final conference of GREENER will be held including presentations related to:

- Project main results and highlights
- Integration of several approaches: Bio-electrochemical hybrid systems
- Long-term ecopiles
- Scaling-up methodology and sustainability aspects
- Main outputs related with dissemination and exploitation &
- Future perspectives.

*Agendas will be announced soon [HERE!](#)

CLUSTERING WORKSHOP

And final GREENER CONFERENCE

28 June 2023

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The GREENER team
Project Coordination team:
University of Burgos – ICCRAM

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ICCRAM
INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH CENTER IN MATERIALS
MATLABS FOR ADVANCED INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGIES

WEBSITE: www.greener-h2020.eu

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